

Extended Methodology for “Rethinking Book Industry Analysis: A Mesosystem Model for Strategic and Institutional Understanding”

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Methodology

Given the substantial volume of interactions derived from **Tool 1** and the insights obtained through **Tool 2**, the most significant contributions from each researcher and professional involved have been synthesized in a general format. To reflect this, Table 2 was created with six columns: the first column provides a numerical list of the 61 participants; the second column records their first and last names; the third column details their area of specialization; the fourth column indicates their participation in the panel of experts and the corresponding phases (1 for the first phase, 2 for the second phase, 3 for the third phase); the fifth column denotes whether they participated in an in-depth interview; and the sixth column uses a coding system to classify the type of contributions made. It is important to highlight that some experts were also interviewees. To accurately interpret the sixth column, the following interpretative keys should be applied, where each number corresponds to a specific type of contribution:

1. Formal contributions to the structure of the article
2. Methodological contributions to the article
3. Conceptual contributions to economic modelling of culture
4. Conceptual contributions to socio-economic characteristics of the Cultural Industries
5. Conceptual contributions to socioeconomic characteristics of the book industry
6. Qualitative information related to their area of professional activity linked to the book industry
7. Contributions to the socioeconomic functions and characteristics of the book
8. Conceptual contributions linked to economic analysis
9. Contributions to the new mesoeconomic analysis model for the book industry

Table

Summary of the phases in which the groups of experts, interviewees and relevant contributions took part.

N. °	Professional	Area of expertise	Panel of experts (Phases in which they take part)	Interview	Relevant contributions
1	Abadal, Ernest	Academic publishing	1		1,4
2	Abril, Luís	Technological companies		yes	6,9
3	Alarcón, Jesús	Graphic arts		yes	6,9
4	Amkie, Lorena	Creation		yes	6,7,9
5	Anta, José Manuel	Distribution / Guild		yes	5,6,7,9
6	Bayle, Albert	Business management	1,2		1,8
7	Beláustegui, Andrés	Publishing / Public Management		yes	6
8	Boixareu, Jeroni	Formative edition		yes	6,8,9
9	Bonilla, Uriel	Points of Sale	1,2,3	yes	1,2,6,9

10	Bravo, Rafael	Researcher / Points of Sale	2		6,9
11	Collado, Luis	Technological companies		yes	6,7,9
12	Cordón, José Antonio	Academic publishing		yes	3,4,5,6,7,9
13	Corroto, Paula	Media		yes	6,9
14	Domingo, Roger	Trade publishing		yes	6,9
15	Dujovne, Alejandro	Academic publishing	1,2,3	yes	1,2,3,5,6,7,9
16	Eguaras, Mariana	Publishing services	2	yes	6,9
17	Fenollar, Marta	Academic publishing		yes	6,9
18	Fernández, Diego	Logistics operator		yes	6,9
19	Gálvez, Ismael	Graphic arts		yes	6,9
20	Gámez, David	Trade publishing		yes	6,9
21	Gil, Francisco	Public Management	1,2,3		1, 2,3,4
22	Gil, Manuel	Consulting / Trade fair management	1,2,3	yes	5,6,7,9
23	Gómez-Escalonilla, Gloria	Researcher / EPCyC	2,3		1,2,3,4,5
24	Jiménez, Javier	Trade publishing		yes	5,6,7,9
25	Sáez, Juan Carlos	Researcher / Trade publishing	2	yes	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,9
26	Kaplan, Daniel	Formative edition		yes	5,6,7,8,9
27	Leibiker, Laura	Trade publishing		yes	6
28	Lizárraga, Jenny	Import / Distribution		yes	6
29	Malumián, Víctor	Trade publishing / Trade fair management	1,2,3	yes	1,3,5,6,7,9
30	María Castro, José	Technological companies		yes	6,9
31	Martí Pidelaserra, Jordi	Researcher / Economics	1,2,3	yes	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9
32	Martínez, Rubén	Researcher / Economía de la cultura	1,2,3		1,2,3,4
33	Mengual, Josep	Researcher / Publishing services		yes	5,6,7,9
34	Merino, Enrique	Points of Sale		yes	5,6,7,9
35	Miró, Lluís	Academic publishing		yes	5,6,7,9
36	Moyano, José	Formative edition / Guild		yes	5,6,7,9
37	Nieto, Ana	Consulting		yes	6
38	Ovejero, Félix	Researcher / Ciencias económicas	1,2		1,2,3
39	Pala, Giaime	Researcher / History of ideas	1		1,2,3
40	Pampín, Juan Manuel	Distribution / Guild		yes	6
41	Pascual Echalecu, Javier	Public administration		yes	5,6,7,9
42	Pérez Gómez, Héctor	Business management	1,2,3		1,2,8,9
43	Ponce, José Luis	Trade publishing		yes	5,6,7,9
44	Pontón, Gonzalo	Trade publishing		yes	3,4,5,6,7,9
45	Portland, Jorge	Consulting		yes	4,5,6,7,9
46	Prieto del Campo, Carlos	Academic publishing	1,2,3	yes	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9
47	Pau Rausell Köster	Researcher / Economics of culture	3		3,4,5,7,8,9

48	Robin, Christian	Researcher / Economics of culture	2		3,4,5,9
49	Rodríguez, Tomás	Trade publishing	2,3		1,4,5,6
50	Rodríguez, Joaquín	Sociology / Economics of publishing	1,2,3		1,2,3,5,6,7,9
51	Rowan, Jaron	Researcher / Economics of culture	1,2,3		1,2,3,4
52	Ruiz Domènech, Bernat	Trade publishing	1,2,3	yes	1,5,6,7,9
53	Sánchez, Miguel Ángel	Graphic arts		yes	6
54	Sánchez, David	Technological companies		yes	6,9
55	Serrano, Alfonso	Trade publishing / Points of Sale	1,2,3	yes	1,3,5,6,7,9
56	Shalzvezon, Guillermo	Literary agent		yes	5,6,7,9
57	Sierra, Francisco	Researcher / EPCyC	1,2,3		1,2,3,4
58	Slachevsky, Paulo	Trade publishing / Graphic arts	2		5,6,9
59	Vázquez, Simón	Trade publishing / Trade fair management	1,2	yes	4,5,6,7,9
60	Vergés, Joaquin	Economics	2		8
61	Walduther, Gabriel	Distribution / Guild		yes	5,6,7,9
62	Zallo, Ramón	Researcher / EPCyC	1,2,3		1,2,3,4,8,9